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Validating a Scale for Measuring Students' Perspectives toward Global Citizenship: A Case at a Private University in Vietnam

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Abstract

Globalization is one of the most significant phenomena of the 21st century, affecting many aspects of human society. In the wave of this influence, higher education institutions in many countries have adjusted themselves in order to prepare their students to be global citizens. However, research shows a need to evaluate whether the integration of global citizenship education is effective among different institutions and contexts. Many scholars are in favor of measuring students' perspectives as a solution. Additionally, although many organizations, such as UNESCO, and other researchers have investigated this issue, the measurement model is mainly designed for large-scale research. Therefore, this study aimed to validate a scale for measuring student perspectives toward global citizenship in a particular context of a university. Notably, the adopted scale measures global citizenship perspectives via three components: social responsibility, global competence, and global civic activism. In the study, each component was measured separately via three smaller measurement models. All the models were validated by using the PLS-SEM approach. The data for validating were collected from 171 students at a private university in Vietnam through an online survey. The result of data analysis suggested that the original scale (which was designed for the context of developed countries) could be employed in the context of developing countries. Nevertheless, some adjustments should be made in term of social responsibility and global competence.

Keywords: Global Citizenship, Students' Perspectives, PLS-SEM, Private University

1. Introduction

1.1 Globalization and global citizenship in higher education curricula

In the context of international cooperation and the advance of technology, globalization has become one of the most massive phenomena globally (Altbach et al., 2004; Yang, 2003). Currently, globalization has considerable

impacts on many aspects of society, especially in the educational field. Many researchers confirm the mutual relationship between globalization and the development of higher education. Firstly, it is apparent that globalization creates a force for higher education development. Notably, Altbach (2013) claims that globalization covers various elements such as society, economy, and technology, which sharpened higher education in the 21st century. Besides, Massey and Burrow (2009) consider globalization as the main factor which fosters higher education development. Secondly, within the context of globalization, it is essential that students need to be well-prepared for more excellent job opportunities or the global competence required (Association of American Colleges & Universities, 2007; Mohajeri Norris & Gillespie, 2009). Hence, plenty of higher education institutions propose to equip their students with skills and knowledge to be global citizens (Clifford & Montgomery, 2017). However, it is challenging for these institutions to conclude an adequate definition of global citizenship or what is needed to be a global citizen (Harrison, 2015; Leask & Bridge, 2013; Oxley & Morris, 2013).

As the requirement of the current situation, global citizenship education has bloomed among higher educational institutions. Resnik (2009), Brown (2003), Dill (2013) and Yemini and Furstenburg (2018) assume global citizenship education as the preparation for students to be more competitive in the global working market as well as other international demands. They also mention that a significant part of applying global citizenship education is integrating global citizen skills into curricula to transform student perspectives towards global issues.

In some countries in Southeast Asia, the need to educate global citizens is much more urgent. Altbach et al. (2004) propose that every nation, particularly the developing one, invests more in the higher education sector to achieve economic development. Torres and Schugurensky (2002) confirm that globalization influences higher education in developing countries and helps these countries embed with the standards to meet the international demands. Taking Vietnam as an example, Vietnamese higher education has experienced great innovation in light of this perspective. Particularly, many universities in Vietnam have increased thanks to globalization (Ministry of Education and Training, 2016). In addition, Nguyen (2011) indicates that the expansion of private universities and the cooperation with overseas higher education institutions create a great force for Vietnam and other developing countries in Asia to integrate global citizenship in their curriculum. Due to this, it is expected that the workforce has been improved in quality. Nevertheless, Nguyen and Tran (2018) and Marginson et al. (2011) indicate that there should be an evaluation of outcomes in order to ensure the global citizenship outcomes among different institutions.

To tackle this issue, many studies have been conducted with attempts to evaluate the success of educating global citizens. The idea of applying transformative learning theory appeared to receive much attention (Green, 2012; Lilley et al., 2015). In general, according to Mezirow (1991), transformative learning refers to the change in human perception and action through the development stages of life. Within learning, human interacts with the world and becomes more respectful to his or her values, purposes and meanings. Basing on this theory, Perry et al. (2013) and Lilley et al. (2015) present the changes in student perspectives as a tool to measure the outcomes of educating global citizens. Regarding large-scale studies, UNESCO and World Survey have distributed some questionnaires with a large number of items in term of measuring participants' perspectives towards global citizenship. However, these scales are difficult for particular institutions or a single researcher to conduct research. For a smaller-scale study, With the efforts of validating appropriate scales for measurement student perspectives as global citizens, Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016) design a questionnaire that focuses on the components of global citizenship, including Social responsibility, Global competence, and Global civic engagement.

1.2 Significance of the problem

As stated above, scholars have confirmed the effects of globalization on higher education development and the essential need of integrating global citizenship into higher education curriculum (Association of American Colleges & Universities, 2007; Dill, 2013; Mohajeri Norris & Gillespie, 2009; Yemini & Furstenburg, 2018). In developing countries such as Vietnam, the integration of global citizenship is significant due to the positive

impacts on increasing productivity, wealth-being, and intellectual competence (Lilley et al., 2017). The World Bank (2020) concludes that Vietnamese higher education has successfully provided global citizenship skills to students. However, there is a gap among different institutions. Hence, validating a measurement model for the outcomes of global citizenship skills in Vietnamese higher education institutions is of importance.

1.3 Global citizenship components

Oxfam Development Education Programme (1997), Caruana (2014) and Atlantic Council for International Cooperation (2014) have concluded that global citizens are a citizen who: (1) have a relatively large amount of knowledge covered broad areas; (2) are open-minded to the whole world as well as aware of the social phenomenon; and (3) have the ability to decide what is right and have the responsibility to make changes for the better world.

In light of this proper definition, a series of studies by Urry (2012), Parekh (2003), Noddings (2005), and (Langran et al., 2009), Morais and Ogden (2011) have presented three components of global citizenship, including:

- Social responsibility referring to the feeling of being responsible for problems and issues happening across the countries and culture, which could create a push for realistic actions for human being sakes;
- Global competence referring to open-mindedness when attempting to learn about other cultures to be effective in communicating and working in an outside environment;
- Global civic engagement referring to the action/ reaction upon any issues at various levels such as local, national, or international one. From these components, the conceptual framework of global citizenship is presented as below:

Figure 1: The components of global citizenship

The authors, then, indicate the measurement model for each component. Firstly, for social responsibility, there are three smaller constructs within, including (1) *Global justice and disparities* (the ability to give an evaluation on issues in society and can realize the examples of global injustice and disparity); (2) *Altruism and empathy* (the ability to manifest some awareness of global issues and respects to the various perspectives towards them); and (3) *Global interconnectedness and personal responsibility* (the ability to deeply understand the correlation between the local action and its global impacts). Secondly, for global competence, three sub-constructs are (1) *Self-awareness* (the ability to realize his or her own limit and make an effort to work successfully in an intercultural environment); (2) *Intercultural communication* (the ability to possess effective communicative strategies to work successfully in the intercultural environment); (3) *Global knowledge* (the ability to keep learning the global issues and phenomena). Lastly, for global civic engagement, three smaller constructs are (1) *Involvement in civic organization* (the ability to volunteer and support international civil agency); (2) *Political*

voice (the ability to establish his/her political point of view basing on the global knowledge he/she has gained); (3) *Global civic activism* (the ability to direct any local action towards the global issues).

1.4 Purpose of the research

This research aimed at validating a scale to measure students' perspectives toward global citizenship at a specific context – a private university in Vietnam. Particularly, the measurement model suggested by Perry et al. (2013), Lilley et al. (2015), Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016) was employed for the validation process.

2. Method

2.1 Setting

This study was conducted at a private university in Vietnam – Van Lang University (VLU). This private university was founded in 1995 to train multiple majors such as engineering, science, economics, and linguistics. Currently, this university provides a huge percentage of new employees for society. Additionally, the university's educational philosophy presents a strong emphasis on the global citizenship outcomes, such as "encouraging our students to live good lives and to be global citizens, making our world a better place" or "making a positive contribution to the local and international community" (Van Lang University, 2020). Hence, this influences the design of all curricula covered by VLU, especially the program outcomes. In order to exam the student perspectives toward global citizenship, a particular curriculum of Bachelor of Arts in English was taken into account. In the program outcomes, the evidence of integrating global citizenship education is identified, i.e., "being able to adjust oneself within the context of globalization" or "contributing to solving the local and global issues" (Faculty of Foreign Languages, 2020, p. 1).

2.2 Sampling Method and Participants

Convenience sampling was employed in the study. Edgar et al. (2017) state that convenience sampling is the common type among non-probabilistic sampling methods. This method is suitable for the researcher who contacts participants within his or her network or through the Internet. What is more, Creswell (2014) and Edgar et al. (2017) indicate that convenience sampling is designed to explore the attitudes of various participants. In the study, 171 students from the Bachelor of Arts in English program were involved.

2.3 Research design

To validate the model for measuring students' perspectives towards global citizenship, the survey study was used as the main research design. Check and Schutt (2011) and Creswell (2014) propose that in the survey study, the attitudes and opinions of the participants are explored via the responses to a set of questions. They also assume that this is the most popular usage of survey study. Therefore, survey study was the suitable design for this research purpose.

2.4 Research instrument

In this study, the main instrument was the questionnaire. According to Creswell (2014) and Ponto (2015), questionnaires are commonly used to explore attitudes, opinions, etc. Additionally, this instrument is of convenience because it could assist the researcher to collect plenty of data in a short time limit and via both online and offline form.

The questionnaire employed in this research was adapted from the validated questionnaire from Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016). Remarkably, the questionnaire consisted of 32 items with some

modifications to the original one such as name of the country or some political policies. All of the items were divided into the following components:

Table 1: Constructs and codes included in the questionnaires

No.	Constructs	Sub-constructs	Number of items	Codes
1	Demographic features	(No)	1	Gen
2	Social responsibility	Global justice and disparities	6	GJD1 → GJD6
		Altruism and empathy	3	AE1 → AE3
		Global interconnectedness and personal responsibility	5	GIPR1 → GIPR5; SR
3	Global competence	Self-awareness	4	SA1 → SA4
		Intercultural communication	6	IC1 → IC6
		Global knowledge	4	GK1 → GK4; GC
4	Global civic engagement	Involvement in civic organizations	5	ICO1 → ICO5
		Political voice	4	PV1 → PV4
		Glocal civic activism	4	GCA1 → GCA3; GCE

Except for the first question on the gender of the participants, all of the other items were responded via a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree) (See Appendix A).

2.5 Data collection & analysis

The online questionnaire was distributed to the participants via MS Teams (Microsoft Teams) and the LMS (Learning Management System) of the university. After finishing collecting the responses from the participants, PLS-SEM approach was employed for data analysis. Hair et al. (2013) and Sarstedt et al. (2017) suggest that PLS-SEM is suitable for examining the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables as well as providing an accurate tool for analyzing quantitative data. Precisely, there were two stages in the data analysis procedure: (1) establishing the measurement model (see Figure 3) and (2) assessing the measurement models.

2.6 Reliability and Validity

To validate the measurement model, some statistical indexes were used, including Outer Factor Loading, Construct Reliability, Convergent Validity (AVE), and Discriminant Validity. Also, the questionnaire was piloted before distributing for data collection to make some adjustments as mentioned in the above section.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Statistic

In the study, there were 171 participants, consisting of 38 males and 133 females. However, in the study, the gender difference was not the focus.

Table 2: Demographic features of the participants

	Number	Percent
Male	38	22.2
Female	133	77.8

3.2 The Assessment of Measurement Models

Figure 2: The measurement models of global citizenship components (Social Responsibility; Global Competence; and Global Civic Activism)

There were three measurement models in this research. Each sub-model was assessed in order to validate the complete measurement model for students' perspectives towards global citizenship. The data of each were analyzed following the procedures of PLS-SEM, including assessing Outer Factor Loading, Construct Reliability (CR), Convergent Validity, and Discriminant Validity.

3.2.1 Social Responsibilities

In term of Outer Factor Loadings, Hair et al. (2013) suggest that all the figures should be 0.7 and above. As a result, the following items were removed in the measurement model for Social Responsibility: GJD3, GJD4, GJD5, GJD6; AE2; GIPR1 GIPR3, GIPR4. Then, GIPR became the latent variable with a single indicator.

Turning to Construct Validity and Convergent Validity figures, after removing the low Out Factor Loading indicators, the results were presented in the following table:

Table 3: The CR and AVE of the measurement model for Social Responsibility

	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
GJD	1.0	1.0
AE	0.756	0.608
GIPR	1.0	1.0

Hair et al. (2013) suggest that the indexes of Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) be assessed. Also, they state that CR should be above 0.7 and AVE should be above 0.5. In the table, it was apparent that the figures met the requirements.

Then, to examine Discriminant Validity, Cross Loadings and HTMT Matrix were used. The table below illustrated the Cross Loading analysis.

Table 4: Cross Loadings of the measurement model for Social Responsibility

	AE	GIPR	GJD
GJD2	0.096	0.263	0.788
GJD1	0.156	0.162	0.669
GIPR4	0.276	1	0.296
AE3	0.829	0.298	0.194
AE1	0.728	0.116	0.055

The cross loadings' square root of any constructs should be higher than any correlation with any different constructs in the model. After examining this, all the figures reached the requirements.

Table 5: The HTMT matrix of the measurement model for Social Responsibility

	AE	GIPR	GJD
GIPR	0.441		
GJD	0.763	0.81	
SR	0.492	0.492	0.783

Regarding the HTMT matrix, all the figures were below 0.85, suggesting that all the indicators had the power of Construct Validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

3.2.2 Global competence

The exact process was done for assessing the measurement model for Global Competence component. Firstly, from the result of Outer Factor Loadings, only two indicators with the factor loading smaller than 0.7 were removed, including IC1 and IC2. Next, the CR and AVE indexes were examined.

Table 6: The CR and AVE of the measurement model for Global Competence

	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
SA	0.840	0.568
IC	0.824	0.547
GK	0.813	0.592

All the figures presented in the table reach the requirements of $CR > 0.7$ and $AVE > 0.5$. Therefore, the process continued with the assessment of Discriminant Validity.

Table 7: Cross Loadings of the measurement model for Global Competence

	GK	IC	SA
GK1	0.713	0.277	0.358
GK2	0.806	0.321	0.472
GK3	0.787	0.359	0.607
IC3	0.388	0.826	0.473
IC4	0.209	0.679	0.165
IC5	0.277	0.545	0.197
IC6	0.349	0.865	0.425
SA1	0.419	0.438	0.707
SA2	0.485	0.276	0.794
SA3	0.441	0.305	0.737
SA4	0.54	0.364	0.772

Table 8: The HTMT matrix of the measurement model for Global Competence

	GC	GK	IC
GK	0.711		
IC	0.572	0.6	
SA	0.672	0.84	0.58

Table 7 showed that the square roots of cross loadings of each construct were higher than the correlation with other constructs. Also, the HTMT matrix figures in Table 8 were smaller than 0.85. Hence, the Discriminant Validity of all the indicators was established.

3.2.3 Global Civic Activism

Lastly, for the measurement model of Global Civic Activism, after examining Outer Factor Loading, all the indicators met the standard; therefore, there was no need to remove any indicators.

Table 9: The CR and AVE of the measurement model for Global Civic Activism

	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ICO	0.902	0.651
PV	0.879	0.646
GCA	0.811	0.590

It was readable from the table that the CR and AVE of this measurement model satisfied the standard numbers. Concerning the Cross Loadings, as shown in Table 10, the square roots of cross loadings of each construct were the biggest in the same row.

Table 10: Cross Loadings of the measurement model for Global Civic Activism

	GCA	ICO	PV
GCA1	0.83	0.368	0.282
GCA2	0.747	0.276	0.173
GCA3	0.724	0.233	0.245
ICO1	0.252	0.744	0.547
ICO2	0.285	0.85	0.588
ICO3	0.321	0.881	0.609
ICO4	0.284	0.86	0.707
ICO5	0.416	0.679	0.425
PV1	0.171	0.609	0.707
PV2	0.153	0.599	0.808
PV3	0.357	0.637	0.85
PV4	0.241	0.526	0.842

Finally, when accessing HTMT Matrix, the results showed that all the figures were under 0.85. Therefore, the measurement model for Global Civic Activism was valid.

Table 11: The HTMT matrix of the measurement model for Global Civic Activism

	GCA	GCE	ICO
GCE	0.487		
ICO	0.504	0.555	
PV	0.374	0.53	0.83

4. Discussion, Conclusion, and Suggestions

4.1 Discussion

Intending to validate a scale for measurement student perspectives towards global citizenship via the validating of measurement models for each component of global citizenship, the result of the study provided some evidence to address this purpose. In term of Outer Factor Loading, the indicators remained in each of three measurement models were illustrated in the following figures:

Figure 3: The measurement models of global citizenship components (Social Responsibility; Global Competence; and Global Civic Activism)

The measurement models of the three components experienced some differences from the original one (see Figure 2). The shaded indicators in Figure 3 referred to the one which was removed because it had a weak power of reflecting the result of the latent variables. It was evident that the first component – Social Responsibility – had the highest number of removed indicators. Notably, the indicators from GJD3 to GDJ6 presented the idea of global justice, such as "all of the places all the Earth are fair" or "No one can't be dominant or have the control of the weaker ones." However, it seemed that the students did not believe in these concepts, compared to the current situation. Also, the indicator from GIPR1 to GIPR3 proposed the concept of personal responsibility, including the possibility of learning from other developed nations or the personal involvement of the injustice of the world. These results were significant different from the validation of Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016, which suggest that these items should be modified in the current context rather than keeping the original ones. With respect to the second component of Global Competence, only two indicators were removed – item IC1 and IC2. These two indicators referred to the cognition and action of adjusting to being suitable with many different multicultural contexts. It could propose that the participants of the current context, a developing country, did not have many opportunities exposing to other foreign cultures. Therefore, when future studies intend to measure this aspect of students' perspectives, adjustments and considerations should be made regarding these items. Surprisingly, this shared the similarity in result of the study from Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016). Lastly, all the indicators of the last measurement model survived after the statistical analysis. Therefore, this measurement model was the most valid one in the study context.

Regarding the criteria of Construct Reliability, Convergent Validity, and Discriminant Validity, after the removal of insignificant indicators in light of Out Loading Factors, all the measurement models met the standards of validity and reliability as Henseler et al. (2015) suggest. As a result, these measurement models were suitable for applying in the context of universities in developing countries.

4.2 Conclusion and suggestions

In the attempt of validating a measurement model for evaluating student perspectives toward global citizenship in the higher education curriculum in a private university in Vietnam, a developing country, the original scale from Morais and Ogden (2011) was employed. There were three smaller components in the original scale, including Social Responsibility, Global Competence, and Global Civic Activism. All of these components were measured in term of three different models (see figure 2), and all these models were assessed and validated via

PLS-SEM approach. The statistical indexes used were Outer Factor Loading Loadings, Construct Validity, Convergent Validity (examined via Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted), and Discriminant Validity (examined via Cross Loadings and HTMT Matrix). The measurement models were distributed to 171 English-major participants in a private university in Vietnam via the form of online questionnaires. After analyzing the collected data, the result showed that among the three components' measurement models, the models of measuring Social Responsibility and Global Competence should be modified and adjusted to fit the context of some developing countries such as Vietnam. What is more, the model of measuring Global Civic Activism appeared to be valid within many contexts, such as this study or the studies of Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016). Hence, this study contributed to the measurement model of global citizenship outcomes in higher education curricula, particularly in the context of some developing nations.

Besides these achievements, the study had its limitations. Firstly, the generalization of the study could be better if the number of participants was larger and in different curricula or universities. However, due to the COVID-19 quarantine time, the questionnaires' distributions and the participants' reach were limited. Therefore, it is recommended that future studies should involve a greater number of participants in various contexts. Finally, this study validating the model of measuring each global citizenship component separately via PLS-SEM approach. Because of the limitation of the knowledge of the author in using PLS-SEM advanced models, it is suggested that future studies could examine the students' perspectives toward global citizenship by the employment of high-order constructs.

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Appendix A

The Research Questionnaire Items with Codes

The questionnaire was adopted from the study of Morais and Ogden (2011) and Roberts and Wilson (2016). All the items are rated from 1 (Totally Disagree) to 5 (Totally Agree).

1. Social responsibility (SR):

1.1. Global justice and disparities (GJD)

GJD1 I think that most people around the world get what they are entitled to have.

GJD2 It is OK if some people in the world have more opportunities than others.

GJD3 I think that people around the world get the rewards and punishments they deserve.

GJD4 In times of scarcity, it is sometimes necessary to use force against others to get what you need.

GJD5 The world is generally a fair place.

GJD6 No one country or group of people should dominate and exploit others in the world.

1.2. Altruism and empathy (AE)

AE1 The needs of the worlds' most fragile people are more pressing than my own.

AE2 I think that many people around the world are poor because they do not work hard enough.

AE3 I respect and am concerned with the rights of all people globally.

1.3. global interconnectedness and personal responsibility (GIPR)

GIPR1 Developed nations have the obligation to make incomes around the world as equitable as possible.

GIPR 2 Vietnamese should emulate the more sustainable and equitable behaviors of other developed countries.

GIPR 3 I do feel responsible for the world's inequities and problems.

GIPR 4 I think in terms of giving back to the global society.

SR Overall, I think I have responsibilities with the global community.

2. Global competence (GC):

2.1. Self-awareness (SA)

SA1 I am confident that I can thrive in any culture or country.

SA2 I know how to develop a place to help mitigate a global environmental or social problem.

SA3 I know several ways in which I can make a difference on some of this world's most worrisome problems.

SA4 I am able to get other people to care about global problems that concern me.

2.2. Intercultural communication (IC)

IC1 I unconsciously adapt my behavior and mannerisms when I am interacting with people of other cultures.

IC 2 I often adapt my communication style to other people's cultural backgrounds.

IC3 I am able to communicate in different ways with people from different cultures.

IC4 I am fluent in more than one language.

IC5 I welcome working with people who have different cultural values from me.

IC6 I am able to mediate interactions between people of different cultures by helping them understand each other's values and practices.

2.3. Global Knowledge (GK)

GK1 I am informed of current issues that impact international relationships.

GK2 I feel comfortable expressing my views regarding a pressing global problem in front of a group of people.

GK3 I am able to write an opinion letter to a local media source expressing my concerns over global inequalities and issues.

GC Overall, I can handle multicultural communication as well as related problems.

3. Global Civic Engagement (GCE):

3.1. Involvement in civic organizations (ICO)

ICO1 Over the next 6 months, I plan to do volunteer work to help individuals and communities abroad.

ICO2 Over the next 6 months, I will participate in a walk, dance, run, or bike ride to support a global cause.

ICO3 Over the next 6 months, I plan to get involved with a global humanitarian organization or project.

ICO4 Over the next 6 months, I plan to get involved in a program that addresses the global environmental crisis.

ICO5 Over the next 6 months, I will pay a membership or make a cash donation to a global charity.

3.2. Political voice (PV)

PV1 Over the next 6 months, I will express my views about international politics on a website, blog, or chat room.

PV2 Over the next 6 months, I will sign an e-mail or written petition seeking to help individuals or communities abroad.

PV3 Over the next 6 months, I will display and/or wear badges/stickers/signs that promote a more just and equitable world.

PV4 Over the next 6 months, I will participate in a campus forum, live music, theater performance, or other events where young people express their views about global problems.

3.3. Glocal civic activism (GCA)

GCA1 If at all possible, I will always buy fair-trade or locally grown products and brands.

GCA2 I will deliberately buy brands and products that are known to be good stewards of marginalized people and places.

GCA3 I will boycott brands or products that are known to harm marginalized global people and places.

GCE Overall, I am willing to participate in global activities in order to handle global issues and support weaker people.